

International Journal of Control Theory and Applications

ISSN : 0974-5572

© International Science Press

Volume 10 • Number 26 • 2017

Modelling of PID controller for AGC of a Multi-Area Power System with Thyristor Controlled Series Controller

K. Swetha¹, D. Vijaya Kumar² and V. S. Vakula³

¹ SRKR College of Engineering, Bheemavaram, Andhra Pradesh-532402, E-mail: swet07@gmail.com

² Aditya Institute of Technology and Management, Tekkali, Andhra Pradesh

³ JNTUK University college of Engineering, Vizianagaram, Andhra Pradesh

Abstract: The current study discusses the impact of non-linearities on “Automatic Generation Control (AGC)” problem with Thyristor Controlled Series Controller (TCSC) system. At the outset, a 3 area thermal power system is considered for investigation in presence of non linearities like “Governor Dead Band (GDB)” as well as “Time Delay (TD)”. In the next step, “Proportional Integral Derivative (PID)” controller is kept as secondary controller and the gains of the controller are optimized by using Bacteria Forging Optimization Algorithm (BFOA). Further, TCSC is incorporated in first area to improve the performance of the system. Finally, from the outcomes of the simulations, it reveals that the power system with TCSC performs better than without any TCSC.

Objectives: To control the frequency deviation efficiently so that it should be in the specified limits and also to show that Thyristor Controlled Series Compensator is better than the conventional methods while considering the non linearities like Governor Dead Band and Time delay

Methods: The methods employed are Particle Swarm Optimisation technique and Bacteria Forging Optimisation Algorithm for tuning the gains of the PID Controller

Findings: The system employed with TCSC performs better than the system does not containing the TCSC. TCSC employed system gives better results when we consider speed governor Dead band, Generation Rate Constraint and Time delay.

Improvements: The change in frequency is less in the areas consisting of TCSC when compared to other frequency Compensating techniques employed areas. So TCSC is a better choice for controlling the frequency deviation in LFC.

Keywords: Load Frequency Control; Thyristor Controlled Series Controller; Particle Swarm Optimization; PIDcontroller; Governor Dead Band; Transport Delay.

1. INTRODUCTION

In modern power system the main concern was about the control of power system even though there are some significant milestones in the evolution of the electric power which is due to demand increases day by day. The